

Analyzing Wine Quality Prediction using Machine Learning Algorithms

Sona Joseph
PG Scholar of
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kerala
sonajolly07@gmail.com

Rony Tom
Asst. Professor of
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kerala
ronytom@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract - Wine classification is a problematic owing to the fact that sight of taste is the poorest recognized of sensory systems. Although manually assessing wine quality takes so long, we may apply machine learning mechanism to determine wine quality in a far more timely and productive manner. During this research, records on red wine quality were employed. To analyze the computational efficiency learning algorithm, we have used accuracy, precision, f1 score, and recall performance measuring matrices. We have used a machine learning technique called Light Gradient Boosting Machine to raise the best accuracy and model.

Keywords – Machine Learning, Random Forest Classifier, Support Vector Machine, Light Gradient Boosting Machine

I. INTRODUCTION

Caliber of winemaking is a vital factor for both users and the industrial sectors. The trait of wine is a very crucial component for buyers as well as for production firms to boost their sales utilizing product quality certification. Using product quality certification, industries are expanding their sales. Formerly, manufacturing quality testing was performed at the end of the phase. This method requires a long - term a substantial amount of resources, such as a need for a range of psychological specialists to assess the enormous expenses of this procedure are tied to product quality. Since each human being has an opinion on the test, judging the wine's quality purely on the basis of human expertise is problematic.

To assure product quality, this chapter investigates ml approaches, like Random Forest Classifier, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Light Gradient Boosting Algorithm.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

K.R. Dahal et al. [1] has implemented the prediction of wine quality using Ridge Regression (RR), Support Vector Machines (SVM), Gradient Boosting Regressor (GBR), and Multi-layer perceptron (MLP), according to the researchers, the evaluation of the result was performed with help of Mean Squared Error (MSE), Correlation Coefficient(R), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MPE). The result outputted from the model performance measurement metrics shows that Gradient Boosting Regressor (GBR) outperformed other three model on the Test dataset with MSE=0.3741, R=0.6057, and MPE=0.0873.

Devika Pawar and Aakansha Mahajan has implemented the prediction of wine quality using the algorithms such as Random Forest Algorithm and Support Vector machine and finally the result comes that the Random Forest Model has given more accurate than the other algorithm.

P. Appalasamy et al., (2012) used physiochemical data to predict wine quality. They employed the decision tree and naive Bayes methods to analyze red and white wine datasets. They evaluate the findings of these two algorithms and come to the conclusion that the categorization strategy can help enhance wine quality during the production process.

Gupta (2018) employed several machine learning algorithms such as linear regression, neural networks, and support vector machine techniques to extract essential aspects from red and white wine quality. To verify the wine's quality, they employed two strategies. First, identifying the target variable's interdependence on the independent variable; second, projecting the target variable's value; and finally, finding that all characteristics are not necessary for the prediction rather than picking only those that are sufficient to predict wine quality.

Paulo Cortez, Juliana Teixeira, and António Cerdeira are three authors. Fernando Almeida Telmo Matos José Reis worked on a research that used Data Mining approaches to analyze wine quality using Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Neural Network (NN). Using a data mining approach, wine tastes are predicted based on readily available analytical tests at the certification stage. With red and white vinhos verdes samples from the Minho region of Portugal, a large dataset was considered. They employed a regression approach to model wine quality in order to retain the order of grades. The SVM model outperformed both the NN and the MR approaches, yielding promising results. The accuracy rates are 64.3 percent and 86.8%, respectively.

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed system has taken the datasets of red wine and use the algorithms like

- Random Forest Classifier
- Support Vector Machine
- Light Gradient Boosting

These algorithms help to find out the accuracy score and the model performance.

A confusion matrix resembles a table model that used in machine learning to illustrate the output of a clustering design on a substantial amount of testing data because of which true parameters are well known. It provides for both the perception of a calculation's presentation. The confusion matrix, crucial quantifiable metrics, and ultimately the correctness predicated here on given dataset is applied to consider numerous data mining algorithms in this study, which leverages the red wine data set.

In researching, these evaluation metrics are being used.

In research, performance measurements are used to estimate and appraise procedures for the purpose to identify their efficacy and effectiveness. Listed below are a handful of them:

- Accuracy: Whenever the combination of True Positive and True Negative is reduced by the summation of True Positive, False Positive, False Negative, and True Negative values inside a confusion matrix, accuracy is anticipated.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+FP+FN+TN}$$

In a confusion matrix, TP stands for True Positive, TN for True Negative, FP for False Positive, and FN for False Negative.

- Precision: Precision is the difference between making the aggregate of True Positive and False Positive values in a confusion matrix by True Positive.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$$

- Recall: Sensitivity is another term for recall. It's the result of dividing True Positive by the confusion matrix's sum of True Positive and False Negative values.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$$

- F-Measure: The F1 Score is obtained by multiplying Precision and Recall by the mean of Precision and Recall in the confusion matrix. The outcome is then categorized into two parts.

$$\text{F1 Score} = \frac{2 * (\text{Recall} * \text{Precision})}{(\text{Recall} + \text{Precision})}$$

A. Techniques involved here are:

Random Forest Algorithm: The supervised learning method is being used by Random Forest, a really well machine learning algorithm. It can be exploited for both classification and regression problems in machine learning. It is based on ensemble learning, which is a methodology of blending diverse classifiers to tackle complex barriers and improve the model's performance.

Support Vector Machine is a supervised predictive model that could be useful to classify and predict data. Cortes and Vapnik described the basic paradigm of SVMs in 1995. The SVM algorithm uses a training set of objects (samples) sorted into classes to discover a hyperplane in the data space that yields the maximal minimum variance (called margin) between entities (samples) that belong to the different classes. As a result, the hyperplane with the largest margin is known as the hyperplane with the largest margin. Instead of using differences in class means, SVM distinguishes objects with using elements (samples) on the margin's edges (called support vectors) (samples).

LightGBM helps to make sure vector approach based on decision trees that optimizes model efficiency by using less memory. It uses two advanced methods: gradient-based One Side Sampling and Exclusive Feature Bundling (EFB), both of which advance on the histogram-based approach used in several GBDT frameworks. While the other algorithms' trees grow horizontally, the LightGBM algorithm climbs vertically, leaf by leaf, whereas the others grow level by level. LightGBM chooses the leaf that has been harmed the most in order to grow. It can cut loss more than a level-by-level strategy by cultivating the same leaf.

IV. BUILD MODEL

There are various steps involved for the prediction of wine quality.

1. Import the packages that are necessary

```
[ ] import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import seaborn as sns
import lightgbm as lgb
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
from lightgbm import LGBMClassifier
from sklearn.svm import SVC
from sklearn.linear_model import SGDClassifier
from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix, classification_report, accuracy_score
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler, LabelEncoder
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split, GridSearchCV, cross_val_score
%matplotlib inline
```

2. Upload the datasets of red wine

```
wine = pd.read_csv('/content/winequality-red.csv')
```

3. Split the dataset in to training and testing dataset

```
x_training_data, x_test_data, y_training_data, y_test_data = train_test_split(x_data, y_data, test_size = 0.25, random_state=42)
```

4. Apply Light Gradient Boosting approach and predict the accuracy score and classification report.

```
#Create model object
model_lgbm = LGBMClassifier()
#Train the model on the training data
model_lgbm.fit(x_training_data, y_training_data)
#Make predictions on the test data.
predictions_lgbm = model_lgbm.predict(x_test_data)
# Calculate the Accuracy Score.
lgbm = accuracy_score(y_test_data, predictions_lgbm)
print(lgbm)
```

```
# Show the classification report.
print(classification_report(y_test_data, predictions_lgbm))
```

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.93	0.97	0.95	347
1	0.76	0.54	0.63	52
accuracy			0.92	399
macro avg	0.85	0.76	0.79	399
weighted avg	0.91	0.92	0.91	399

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The red wine datasets used to forecast wine quality are provided in the dataset. Multiple machine learning approaches being deployed in this report's dataset. It assists when it comes to determining the precision of algorithms as well as choosing the most effective amongst those from a series of datasets. While being used, the data is broken into 2 sets: a training set and a testing set. These results reveal that the accuracy gained for the training and testing sets using Random Forest Algorithm is about 0.90 percent, whereas the accuracy obtained using the SVM algorithm is about 0.88 percent, indicating that the Random Forest Model delivers the most correct score and model. So, to obtain the accuracy score and model performance, I use a new machine learning approach called Light Gradient Boosting Machine. When these three algorithms are compared, we find that the Light Gradient Boosting Machine has the highest accuracy score of the three.

A. Implementation

CONCLUSION

Based on the comparison of these three algorithms we come to a conclusion that by comparing these three algorithms the Light Gradient Boosting Machine Approach has more accurate and faster for predicting the accuracy score for the red wine datasets and also gives a better model performance than Random Forest Algorithm. When compared to random forest, LightGBM is frequently found to perform better. When compared to random forest, correctly adjusted In terms of speed and quality, LightGBM will most probably still win. When contrasted to Random Forest Classifier, it is more developed and has many more advantages, such as faster speed and agility training more efficiency, Poor memory consumption, greater precision, Parallel, distributed, and GPU learning are all supported. Capable of processing large volumes of data.

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